

Table 5

Grid 3. Links by STEM teachers on YouTube Spain to other channels, by gender and quantity

Gender	Channel	Number of channels linked	Channels with man	Channels with woman	Channels with man and woman
Man	48. <i>Ciencia XL</i>	8	6	1	1
Man	54. <i>Huele a Química</i>	12	9	3	0
Man	21. <i>QuantumFracture</i>	Woman that links with:		1	0
Woman	<i>TheQuantumFracture</i>	12	9	1	2
Man	62. <i>FISICALIMITE</i>	7	6	1	0
Woman	67. <i>Sábados culturetas</i>	5	5	0	0
Man	68. <i>CienciadeSofa</i>	3	2	1	0
	TOTAL	36	28	7	1